

TEXTUAL METAFUNCTIONS OF AWARD-WINNING SHORT STORIES: DEVELOPING A THEME-BASED FRAMEWORK FOR TEACHING WRITING

Israel C. Bual

Department of Education, Schools Division of Bohol, Candijay District, Candijay Municipal High School, Poblacion, Candijay, Bohol, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15034459>

ABSTRACT

This study is to analyze the first paragraphs of three Don Carlos Palanca award-winning short stories to develop a theme-based framework for teaching writing. The first paragraphs were chosen because they can establish the information flow. The researcher perceived this as an advantage, especially in teaching novice writers to help them construct cohesive paragraphs. The study is limited only to the selected Filipino writers who received the first prize in the Don Carlos Palanca Memorial Awards for Literature. The following works were selected with their corresponding authors and year: “Phallic Symbols” by Abola, Alexis A.L., 2015; “Zoetrope” by Cornelio, Richard C., 2016; and, “Disguise” by Bengan, John., 2017. The selected winning pieces belong to the short stories category. The researcher utilized short stories instead of other literary genres because short stories are given to the students to integrate the lessons into the English subject. The researcher used content analysis to focus on the interpretation and understanding of the three award-winning short stories by analyzing the thematic selection and thematic progression. This design is appropriate for use in this study because it extracted meaningful information from the texts. Based on the analysis of the thematic selection and thematic progression of the first paragraphs of Don Carlos Palanca's first-prize award in literature pieces, it can be concluded that cohesive texts can create communicative outcomes. It can reflect the message the writer wants to imply. It was concluded that it can help students achieve cohesion in writing when integrated into writing classes.

Keywords: *Split, Theme, Rheme, Metafunction, Progression*

INTRODUCTION

The functional grammar approach has been appealing in the field of education. It received more attention to researchers in the field of English Language Teaching since it was developed by Halliday in the 1970s. Recently, it has evolved into systemic-functional model developed by Halliday (2004) which focuses on the explanation of language as a system. Moreover, it is a semiotic approach to the language which views it as network of meanings that has interrelated options in making meaning and the meaning of the language itself.

According to Feng (2013), functional grammar has been found to pedagogically facilitate the students in successfully achieving academic registers. Meaning, students were able to achieve understanding on other concepts because of the understanding of functional grammar.

Textual metafunction in this study focused on thematic selection and thematic progression, is anchored on Halliday's (1985) systemic-functional model, and classified theme into three categories. These categories are ideational, textual, and interpersonal. In terms of thematic progression, the study adopts Paltridge's classification of thematic progression. The theme progression is classified into three types, namely constant pattern, linear pattern, and multiple theme pattern. The thematic progression shows progression and cohesion towards the text.

Halliday (1985) explains that all the written and oral discourses inherit these three metafunctions; ideational, textual, and interpersonal metafunctions. These categories perform different function in clauses. It is important to develop awareness on textual metafunction because it can establish coherence between and among clauses in a paragraph.

Brown and Hood (1989) state that the writing process depends on different factors: who you are writing to (reader), why are you writing (purpose), what are you writing about (content), where are you, how much time you have, how you feel, etc. (situation). Furthermore, they introduce and explain the three stages of preparing to write, while you are managing the time and skill to write, drafting, while one is beginning to write, and revising, while you compare what you need to say, with what you have said, to check if you really said everything you were determined to say. However, Atlee (2005) believes that there are five stages in each writing process, including pre-writing, composing, revising, editing and publishing.

Writing is one of the macro skills in language that allows the user of the language to clearly convey the message in written format. Writing involves skills in the cognitive domain which includes learning, comprehension, and application and synthesis of new knowledge (Defazio et al., 2010). It shows that effective writing is achieved when one has a good command of the language. According to Graham (2019), learning how to write is essential for the student's success in school, at work, and in their personal lives. This skill is however not developed in an instant.

The students must develop their writing skills through practice. Afrin (2016) also stated that writing skill is essential in communication for the students in their entire academic life because it enables them to express their thoughts clearly through well-constructed texts. Cohesive ideas in writing enable writers to express their message clearly. Concerning theme and thematic progression, Jing (2015) emphasized that it is a major aspect that equips the writers in constructing their messages that fit smoothly.

Several researches reveal that Filipino learners encounter difficulty in expressing their ideas through writing. According to Saavedra (2020), conveying and organizing ideas are among the challenges encountered by Filipino learners in writing. Ulit (2018) revealed that students have persistent errors in writing in terms of structural and grammatical category. It shows that there is a problem with the students' thought construction and organization in writing. This is also supported by Pablo and Lasaten (2018) who found out that students are having difficulty in writing especially in presenting the content and organization of ideas.

Writing difficulty can also be observed among the Grade 9 learners in Candijay Municipal High School. The errors manifested in the students' written outputs in English. The challenges encountered in writing urged the researcher to examine the structure of the first paragraphs of award-winning short stories to craft a theme-based framework in teaching writing. The theme-based framework focused on thematic selection and thematic structure.

Research Questions

The study aimed to find out the textual metafunction of selected Filipino writers of award-winning short stories towards developing a theme-based framework for teaching writing.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the types of Thematic Selections used in the first paragraphs of the Don Carlos Palanca award-winning short stories of Filipino writers?
2. What are the aspects of thematic progressions employed in the first paragraphs of the Don Carlos Palanca award-winning short stories of Filipino writers?
3. Based on the findings of the study, what theme-based framework for teaching writing in English may be developed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the qualitative research design particularly content analysis. The researcher used content analysis to focus on the interpretation and understanding of the three award-winning short stories by analyzing the thematic selection and thematic progression. This design is appropriate to be used in this study because it extracted meaningful information from the texts. The thematic selection and thematic progression were extracted from the texts and analyzed how the authors applied these concepts in their works.

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized the first paragraph of the Don Carlos Palanca award-winning short stories in the analysis of thematic selection and thematic progression. The object of having short texts is that it enables the researcher to deal with the texts as a whole within the scope of the story. Furthermore, the first paragraph serves as the starting point of idea presentation and hooking up the readers' attention. The first paragraph is ideal for analysis because it features the preliminary information about the text.

All texts were analyzed using the Model of Halliday (1985). There are three kinds of themes: ideational or topical, textual, or interpersonal. The ideational themes are further categorized as unmarked or marked. Unmarked themes are grammatical sentence subjects or declarative clauses, and can be realized as simple and complex nominal groups. The marked themes are further sub-categorized into three types: circumstantial adjunct, subordinating clause, and attributive clause.

Analyzing the thematic progression of the short stories was based on the Paltridge's classification of thematic progression.

The researcher used this tool in the analysis of the texts. The analysis is presented in tabular form. The words are categorized into different columns.

Research Procedure

Data Analysis. The researcher selected the award-winning short stories from the Don Carlos Palanca awards official website. The researcher picked the first prize awardees. The researcher selected the following short stories: "Phallic Symbols" written by Alexis Abola, the 2015 first prize awardee; "Zoetrope" by Richard C. Cornelio, the 2016 first prize awardee; and, "Disguise" by John Bengan, the 2017 first prize awardee.

The researcher extracted the first paragraphs of the short stories. The first paragraphs were chosen because it is the first stage of establishing the flow of information of the story. Since it is the starting point, it is essential to understand how the award-winning writers establish the flow of information of their text.

After identifying the short stories, the researcher extracted the clauses of each first paragraph. For each clause, the theme-rheme boundary was identified. The researcher carefully identified the themes based on their function in the sentence. The researcher used tabulation to extract the functions of the words in each clause to thoroughly examine the boundary between the theme and rheme. The researcher labelled the different themes used in each clause. The following are the labels used: ideational, textual theme, and topical theme.

After determining the themes, the researcher then analyzed the thematic structure. The researcher extracted the themes and its corresponding rheme. The arrows were used to determine the coherence of the themes and rhemes between the clauses.

With the data generated from the analysis, the researcher developed the proposed theme-based framework. The proposed framework aims to provide the teachers and learners the concept of the structure of cohesive text.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings generated from the analysis of thematic structure and thematic progression are presented in this chapter. It highlights the frequency of thematic selection in the first paragraphs of the three selected Don Carlos Palanca award-winning short stories and the thematic progression applied by the authors.

Thematic Selections Found in the Texts

Tables 1 to 3 present the Thematic selections employed by the authors in the texts analyzed in this study. The theme was categorized based on Halliday and Matthiesen (2004) which includes the topical theme being the obligatory theme, textual, and interpersonal being the optional themes. According to the frequency analysis, there are 52 clauses found in the three selected short stories. There are 15 clauses for “Zoetrope”, 12 clauses for “Disguise” and 25 clauses for “Phallic Symbols”.

The following are clauses with simple themes for the story of “Zoetrope”: 1, 6, and 9. There were no simple marked theme found in the first paragraph of this short story. Below are the simple unmarked themes found in the short story:

- (1) Joaquin # reasoned. (“Zoetrope”, clause 1)
- (2) He # was the sort of person (“Zoetrope”, clause 6)
- (3) He # was an expert cumpornographer. (“Zoetrope”, clause 9)

Table 1. Thematic Analysis of the First Paragraph of “Zoetrope” by Richard C. Cornelio

Title of the Clause Short Story	Topical/Ideational		Themes Textual				Textual/Interpersonal		Interpersonal		
	Adverbial Group	Adjunct Group	Marked Complement Common or Proper Noun as Head	Unmarked Conjunctives External	Conjunctions		Wh- elements	Modal/ Comment Adjunct	Vocative	Finite/Verbal	Rheme
					Internal	Conjunctive Adjuncts					
“Zoetrope”			Joaquin								
1			It	that							reasoned
2			Kids in their formative years	that							had to do with the linguistic excess had to compensate for with imaginary narratives
3			They [ellipsis]								[are] simply outrageously outlandish and silly.
4		which were	he	and				more often than not	would		say that.
5			He					of course			was the sort of person
6			He								sure to trot out some theory of
7			He [ellipsis]				Who			Would be	evolution or quote Darwin after watching a herd of elephants fly like flumoxed chickens.
8			He								was an escort-cartomographer, thought with his big head
9			he	but							Had always valued a sound explanation for stuff that challenged evidence.
10			He [ellipsis]	and				no pun intended			I had to disagree
11		This time						though			It was, coincidentally sometime
12				because							Had decided to separate for good
13			Joaquin and I	after							
14			Clay	that							Began talking about his imaginary brother named Buddy.

Based on the clauses above, the ‘#’ signals the boundary of theme and rheme. The theme in clause 1 utilized a proper noun that functions as topical unmarked theme. The same with clauses 6 and 9, the author made use of a pronoun as the topical theme. It contributes to the coherence of ideas in the paragraph because the pronouns do not have missing antecedents. It manifests the careful use of pronouns to refer to the nouns they modify.

There are 13 clauses that have multiple themes. Among the multiple themes in the story, the three clauses are marked.

- (1) which were, more often than not, simply outrageously outlandish and silly. (“Zoetrope”, clause 4)
- (2) of course, he would say that. (“Zoetrope”, clause 5)
- (3) This time, though, # I had to disagree. (“Zoetrope”, clause 12)

Halliday (1994) defined marked theme as “an element that occupies the point of departure position of the clause and conflates with the grammatical subject”. In clause 4, the marked theme functioned as complement having pronoun ‘which’ as the head. The marked theme ‘of course’ from clause 5 functioned as a comment adjunct under adverbial group. In clause 12, the theme ‘this time’ is marked. It functioned as a complement having pronoun as the head. The marked themes conflate with the grammatical subject of their respective clauses.

The comment adjunct “though” functioned as the speaker’s transition to impose restriction to be expressed via the marked theme of the clause. It was also used to imply a previous agreement done by the speaker in the story. The comment adjunct in the sentence carries appraisal meaning. It adds to the meaning of the text. It is related with the findings of Li (2021) that emphasize on comment adjunct. It was found out that comment adjuncts are rich in appraisal meanings that relates to the speaker’s subjectivity. It is also supported by Fang (2018) who described comment adjunct as the speaker’s opinion towards what he says. It shows that the function of ‘though’ in the clause, although an adjunct, carries linguistic meaning that adds to the realization of the text.

The following are the clauses with modal or comment adjuncts in the theme:

- (1) which were, more often than not, simply outrageously outlandish and silly (“Zoetrope”, clause 4)
- (2) no pun intended – and had always valued a sound explanation for stuff that challenged evidence. (“Zoetrope”, clause 10)

Ellipse occurred in the text in the dependent clauses. The following are the clauses with ellipse unmark topical/ ideational theme:

- (1) which were, more often than not [they] simply outrageously outlandish and silly. (“Zoetrope”, clause 4)
- (2) [he] who would be sure to trout some theory of evolution or quote Darwin after watching a herd of elephants fly like flummoxed chickens (“Zoetrope”, clause 7)

(3) no pun intended – [he] had always valued a sound explanation for stuff that challenged evidence (“Zoetrope”, clause 10)

Table 2 presents the thematic analysis of the first paragraph of “Disguise” by John Bengan. The first paragraph has 15 clauses. Among the clauses, there were six identified simple themes.

- (1) I # gestured her to wait. (“Disguise”, clause 2)
- (2) I # had to go to the intersection near the bridge. (“Disguise”, clause 4)
- (3) She # told me to take her to a middle-income subdivision. (“Disguise”, clause 6)
- (4) We # were cruising at sixty kilometers. (“Disguise”, clause 7)
- (5) She # grasped. (“Disguise”, clause 10)
- (6) I # greeted her good evening, glancing at the rear-view mirror. (“Disguise”, clause 15)

The first-person pronouns were used as simple themes in the first paragraph of the story. It reveals the first-person point-of-view of the story. The use of pronouns was also coherent to the rest of the clauses which shows the consistency of the author in writing. According to Mulcahy and Gouldthorp (2015), the use of first-person narrative point of view promotes empathy among the readers as they read unfamiliar events from the story.

There is one interrogative sentence in the story. It has multiple themes.

- (1) Is that really # you? (“Disguise”, clause 9)

The interrogative sentence, according to Halliday and Matthiessen (2004), this type of interrogative sentence exhibits what polarity does the speaker wants to know. Table 4 labelled the theme “is” as interrogative yes/ no. It has an indicative mood.

There are three minor clauses identified in the first paragraph of Disguise. These clauses were included in the clause count but they have no thematic structure.

- (1) “Hala ka! (“Disguise”, clause 11)
- (2) “Hala ka uy!” (Disguise, clause 13)
- (3) “Maayong gabii!” (Disguise”, clause 14)

According to Halliday and Matthiessen (2004), minor themes are clauses without mood. It typically functions as greetings, exclamations and alarms, and calls. The three minor clauses identified were “Bisaya” terms. The first minor clause “Hala ka!” has an equivalent of “oh!” in English. The same goes with “Hala ka uy!” with “uy” as an additional which intensifies the emotion depicted in the line. The “Maayong gabii” minor clause is a greeting which can be translated as “Good evening”. These clauses have no thematic structure. Although Halliday and Matthiessen (2004) emphasized that these minor clauses are not regarded as clauses, they were included in the clause count.

Table 2. Thematic Analysis of the First Paragraph of “Disguise” by John Bengan

Title of the Short Story	Themes														
	Topical/Ideational				Textual			Textual/interpersonal		Interpersonal					
	Marked	Adjunct	Prepositional Group	Complement Common or Proper Noun Yes/no as Head	Pronoun as Head	Unmarked	Continuatives	External	Internal	Conjunctive Adjuncts	Wh-elements	Modal/Comment Adjunct	Vocative	Finite/Verbal	Rheme
found															
1					A woman on the other side of the road										summoned me.
2					I										gestured her to wait
3					I										could not
4					I										make a U-turn. had to go to the intersection near the bridge
5															I thought immediately: are those biodegradable?
6					She										told me to take her to a middle-income subdivision.
7					We										were cruising at sixty kilometers.
8					She								finally		recognized me
9				Is	that										you?
10					She										grasped
11															
12					It										is really you
13															
14															
15					I										greeted her good evening glancing at the rear-view mirror.

There is one marked theme identified in the first paragraph. The theme is headed by adverbial.

(1) Later when she climbed into the vehicle, carrying plastic grocery bags, # I thought immediately: Are those biodegradable? (“Disguise”, clause 5)

This structure signifies that the speaker is giving emphasis on the arrangement of ideas in the paragraph. The theme carries cohesive property which relates it with the previous clause by emphasizing the time as the signal for the transition of events in the story.

There are three multiple themes identified in the first paragraph of “Disguise”.

- (1) because I could not # make a U-turn. (“Disguise”, clause 3)
- (2) when she finally # recognized me. (“Disguise”, clause 8)
- (3) is that really # you? (“Disguise”, clause 12)

The multiple themes have unmarked topical themes. The clauses features the use of external conjunctions such as “because” and “when” in clauses 3 and 8 respectively. The finite “could not” was also used showing negative polarity of the clause which is evident in clause 3. The modal/ comment adjuncts “finally” and “really” from clause 8 and 9 respectively signals the personal remark of the speaker towards the topic. This exhibits the coherence in writing of the author through integrating the first-personal pronouns with the personal remarks as shown in the use of comment adjuncts.

Table 3 highlights the thematic structure of the first paragraph of the story “Phallic Symbols” by Exie Abola. The table shows that there are 27 clauses in the first paragraph. Among the clauses, there are seven simple themes, 19 with multiple themes, and two minor clauses.

The following clauses have simple theme.

- (1) Bettina Galang # said she’d rather be dead than fat (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 1)
- (2) That # is a bit extreme (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 2)
- (3) I [ellipse] # am hoping (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 13)
- (4) Bettina # is worried (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 16)
- (5) She # is not (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 20)
- (6) The other half # is mine, thanks (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 26)
- (7) The rest of the day # is coffee and cigarettes (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 27)

The clause 1 established the connection between the clauses in the first paragraph of the short story. The ellipse topical theme “I” is an unmarked theme. The theme is ellipse because of the presupposition from the previous clause.

- (1) I would # slash my gut instead. (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 12)

Table 3. Thematic Analysis of the First Paragraph of “Phallic Symbols” by Exie Abola

Title of the Short Story	Clause/ Line found	Themes			Textual			Textual/ Interpersonal		Interpersonal		Rheme	
		Topical/ Ideational		Complement Common or Proper Noun as Head	Nominalization	Unmarked	Continuatives	Conjunctions		Wh- elements			
		Marked Adjunct	Prepositional Group					External	Internal	Conjunctive Adjuncts	Interrogative		relative
“Phallic Symbols”	1			Bettina Gabang								said she'd rather be dead than fat.	
	2			That								is a bit extreme	
	3			I			but					understand	
	4			she			Where					is coming from	
	5			I				if				think about all the crazy things	
	6			It			that					happen to me	
	7			It (ellipse)									
	8			It (ellipse)			yeah						is getting fat
	9			It (ellipse)									horrible
	10			I									want to slash my wrists
	11			I			well, no						like being alive too much.
	12			I									slash my gut instead
	13			I (ellipse)									am hopping
	14			The fat									
	15			I									spill out
	16			Bettina				but			seriously		think about it
	17			Her boyfriend Jobert				because					is worried
	18												had a string of really skinny girlfriends, all models, and older than her too
	19			she				before					came along
	20			she									thinks she's fat?
	21			she									is not
	22			She				but					watches her weight a lot
	23			she									eat half a pizza for lunch
	24			She (ellipse)				then					worry the rest of the day
	25			it									show
	26			The other half									is mine, thanks
	27			The rest of the day									is coffee and cigarettes

The pronoun “I” in clause 12 is omitted because the previous clause, clause 11, used “I” as the unmarked topical theme. The topical themes revealed the first-person point-of-view of the story. The narrator is one of the characters in the story at the same time the teller of the story. In terms of coherence, the use of proper nouns “Bettina Galang” and “Bettina” as antecedent and second person pronoun leads to better understanding of the paragraph.

It is remarkable that there are no marked themes used in the first paragraph of the short story. The clauses are in declarative form. According to Halliday and Matthiesen (2004), unmarked themes are common in declarative sentences as the subject of the sentence is also its theme. It shows that the theme, subject, and the performer of the action are conflated into a single element. Furthermore, it is the usual form writers take in writing when there is no prior context leading up to it, and no other reasons for choosing other forms.

There are 8 clauses that have finite/ verbal under interpersonal themes.

- (1) that # could happen to me (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 6)
- (2) it [ellipsed] would be # horrible (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 9)
- (3) I would # want to slash my wrist (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 10)
- (4) I would # slash my gut instead (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 12)
- (5) The fat would # spill out (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 14)
- (6) but seriously, I would # think about it (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 15)
- (7) she will # eat half a pizza for lunch (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 23)
- (8) if it will # show (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 25)

Interpersonal theme according to Paldtridge (2006) indicates relation between the participants and the text, position, point of view, that is being taken the clause. The finite verbs have communicative function in each clause. The modals could, would, and will function as the finite verbs in the clauses. In the study of Vethamani et al. (2008), it was emphasized that learners perceive the conceptual meaning of sentences through the use of modals. In relation to the study, the use of finite verbs in the clauses help the readers comprehend the logical relations of the clauses and thus leading to the understanding of the text.

A comment adjunct is also identified in the short story. Comment adjunct belongs to interpersonal theme category. It also signals a communicative function. In the context of the story, it expresses the comment of the speaker towards the topic. Below is the comment adjunct in the short story:

- (1) but seriously, I would # think about it. (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 15)

External conjunctions are seen to occur more in this paragraph compared with the other two short stories. This reveals the writing style of the author. Subsequently, it also reveals

the cohesion among the clauses these external conjunctions connect. The following clauses have external conjunctions:

- (1) but I # understand (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 3)
- (2) where she # is coming from (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 4)
- (3) that could # happen to me (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 6)
- (4) but seriously, I would # think about it (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 15)
- (5) because her boyfriend Jobert # had a string of really skinny girlfriends, all models, and older than her too (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 16)
- (6) before she # came along (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 17)
- (7) but she # watches her weight a lot (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 21)
- (8) then # worry for the rest of the day (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 23)

Martin and Rose (2007) emphasized that external conjunctions emphasize logical relations between clauses. In the clauses above, it can be seen that the external conjunction was used to link one clause to another.

According to Halliday and Hasan (1976) the textual theme is the text-forming component in the linguistic system. This implies that textual themes function as cohesive devices to connect the theme and rheme of the clauses. Another textual theme identified in the short story is the use of continuatives. Continuatives, according to Halliday and Matthiesen (2004), are small set of words that signal the movement in discourse. It could be a response, in dialogue, or a new point leading to the movement to the next point of the speaker. Below are the examples of the continuatives found in the short story:

- (1) yeah # getting fat (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 7)
- (2) well, no, I # like being alive too much (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 11)

According to Halliday and Hasan (1976), continuatives are like conjunctions that are used with cohesive force in the text but do not express any conjunctive relations. In the texts analyzed in the study, the continuatives was used as the same speaker connects the previous statement. The continuatives also connected the theme from the previous rheme which adds coherence to the text.

There are two minor clauses identified in the first paragraph of the short story. It is included in the clause count but not regarded as a clause with thematic content. It has the same implication with the other short stories analyzed in this study. The following are the minor clauses found in the text:

- (1) as in, really big mama fat (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 8)
- (2) no, not at all (“Phallic Symbols”, clause 21)

Analysis of Thematic Progression

The analysis of thematic progression covers the connection between the theme and rheme of every clause in relation to the theme and rheme of other clauses. The

analysis is done through arrows that point out to the connected theme and rheme. The type of thematic progression is determined through the overall progression that the paragraphs consist.

Table 4 shows the thematic progression of the first paragraph of “Zoetrope”. The table reveals that there are multiple thematic progression patterns in the paragraph.

There are two thematic patterns identified in the short story “Zoetrope”. These patterns are linear theme pattern and theme reiteration pattern. The linear theme pattern is observed in the thematic progressions of the clauses 1 to 5. The rheme in the clause 1 is connected with the external conjunction “that” in clause 2. The same with the rheme of clause 2, it is connected with external conjunction “that” of clause 3. The rheme of clause 3 is what the marked theme “which were” refers to, hence, they are connected. The external conjunction “and” was also used to link the rheme of clause 4 to the theme of clause 5.

Theme reiteration pattern is observed in clause 1 and clause 5. The proper name “Joaquin” from clause 1 is being referred to as “he” in clause 6. Then, linear theme pattern is identified in clauses 6 to 7. The rheme of clause 6 is connected with the relative pronoun “who” of the theme of clause 7.

Theme reiteration pattern is also observed between the theme of clause 1 and the theme of clause 8. The topical theme “Joaquin” is the antecedent of pronoun “he”. Linear pattern is observed in clauses 8 to 14. The connection between the theme and rheme of the clauses were joined by the use of conjunction. However, the rheme of clause 10 is connected with the theme of clause 11 marked theme “This time” and comment adjunct “though”. The marked theme “this time” provided transition in terms of time and the comment adjunct “though” intensified the connection between the rheme of the previous clause and the theme of the succeeding clause.

It is evident that the use of conjunctions and proper use of pronouns are essential in establishing coherence among the clauses of the paragraph. According to Halliday and Matthiesen (2004), conjunctions are markers that indicate the relationship of a clause to a previous one. It shows that conjunctions bind the thought of the clauses. Meanwhile, the use of appropriate pronouns help the readers follow the flow of the story. In the context of the study, the name “Joaquin” was consistently labeled as “he” and there are no other “he” in the paragraph other than Joaquin. It implies that the reader will not mistakenly identify other proper nouns in the paragraph aside from Joaquin.

Table 4. Thematic Progression of “Zoetrope”

Title of the Short Story	Clause/line found	Theme	Type of Progression	Rheme
"Zoetrope"	1	Joaquin		reasoned
	2	that it		had to do with the linguistic excess
	3	that kids in their formative years		had to compensate for with imaginary narratives
	4	which were, more often than not, [they]		[are] simply outrageously outlandish and silly.
	5	And, of course, he would		say that.
	6	He		was the sort of person
	7	who would be		sure to trout out some theory of evolution or quote Darwin after watching a herd of elephants fly like flummoxed chickens.
	8	He		was an escort cumpornographer .
	9	but he		thought with his big head
	10	-no pun intended- and [he] <i>ellipse</i>		had always valued a sound explanation for stuff that challenged evidence.
	11	This time, though, I		had to disagree,
	12	because, it		was coincidentally sometime
	13	after Joaquin and I		had decided to separate for good
	14	that Clay		began talking about his imaginary brother named Buddy.

Legend:

- Linear Pattern
- Theme reiteration
- - - Split Theme Pattern

Table 5 presents the thematic progression of the first paragraph of the short story “Disguise”. The data reveals that there are three types of patterns employed in the paragraph. The following are the patterns identified: two linear patterns, four theme reiteration pattern, and split theme.

The linear patterns were observed in the clauses 1 to 2 and clauses 8 to 9. In the case of the rheme of clause 1 and theme of clause 2, the pronoun “me” from the rheme of clause 1 becomes the topical theme “I” of clause 2. Then, for clauses 8 to 9, the rheme of clause 8 becomes the interrogative yes/no marked theme of clause 9.

Table 5. Thematic Progression of “Disguise”

Short Story	Clause/line found	Theme	Type of Progression	Rheme
"Disguise"	1	A woman on the other side of the road		summoned me.
	2	I		gestured her to wait
	3	because I could not		Make a U-turn
	4	I		had to go to the intersection near the bridge
	5	Later when she		climbed into the vehicle, carrying plastic grocery bags
	6	She		told me to take her to a middle income subdivision
	7	We		<u>were</u> cruising at sixty kilometers,
	8	when she finally		recognized me.
	9	"Is that		you?"
	10	she		grasped
	11	(Minor clause) Hala ka,		
	12	it		is really you.
	13	(Minor clause) Hala ka uy!		
	14	(Minor clause) "Maayong Gabii",		
	15	I		greeted her good evening, glancing at the rear-view mirror.

Legend:

- Linear Pattern
- Theme reiteration
- Split Theme Pattern

Theme reiteration pattern is mostly used in the first paragraph of the short story. There were four instances where theme reiteration was observed. The theme “A woman on the other side of the road” of clause 1 is the topical theme “she” in clause 5. It is also the topical theme of the themes of clauses 6, 7, and 10. The theme “I” of clause 2 is also the topical theme for clause 4.

The split theme pattern was also identified in the short story. The rheme of clause 8 becomes the theme “it” of clause 12 and topical theme “I” of clause 15. The text may seem complicated because of different themes the clauses present. But, it can be observed that the proper use of pronouns to refer to its antecedent play an important role in the logical presentation of the flow of the story. The process may seem complicated but

can help readers establish understanding of the text. Fang and Li (2015) emphasized that complicated texts tend to use multiple thematic patterns because it aims to develop logical relations and establishes its context. The use of multiple thematic patterns of the three award-winning short stories signifies that the authors are developing logical relations among their ideas.

Table 6. Thematic Progression of “Phallic Symbols”

Short Story	Clause/line found	Theme	Type of Progression	Rheme
"Phallic Symbols"	1	Bettina Galang		said she'd rather be dead than fat.
	2	That		is a bit extreme,
	3	but I		understand
	4	where she		is coming from.
	5	If I		think about all the crazy things
	6	that [it]		could happen to me,
	7	Yeah, [it]		[is] getting fat
	8	(minor clause) as in, really big mama fat		
	9	[it] would be		horrible
	10	I would		want to slash my wrists
	11	Well, no, I		like being alive too much
	12	I would		slash my gut instead
	13	[I]		[am] hoping
	14	The fat would		spill out
	15	but seriously, I'd		think about it
	16	Bettina		is worried
	17	because her boyfriend Jobert		had a string of really skinny girlfriends, all models, and older than her too
	18	before she		came along
	19	What if she		thinks she's fat?
	20	She		is not.
	21	(minor clause) not at all		
	22	but she		watches her weight a lot.
	23	she will		eat half a pizza for lunch
	24	then [she]		worry the rest of the day
	25	if it will		show
	26	(The other half		is mine, thanks.)
	27	The rest of the day it		is coffee and cigarettes.

Legend:

- Linear Pattern
- Theme reiteration
- - - - Split Theme Pattern

Table 6 shows the thematic progression of the first paragraph of the short story “Phallic Symbols”. There are four linear theme patterns, seven theme reiteration patterns, and two split theme patterns identified in the first paragraph.

The linear patterns were observed in clauses 1 to 4, clauses 16 to 18, The use of conjunctions was essential in the connection between the rheme and theme of the previous clause to the succeeding clause. In the study of Lahuerta (2015), the use of conjunctions in composition is associated with writing quality. It supports the function of conjunction as cohesive device that links ideas and concepts of the sentences. In the context of this study, the conjunctions were the important factors leading to linear theme pattern of the clauses.

The theme “Bettina Galang” of clause 1 and the pronoun “she” as the theme in clause 4 are connected through the proper use of pronoun. The pronoun “she” refers to Bettina Galang. However, in clause 16, pronoun “she” was not used but instead the author used the first name “Bettina”. It shows a theme reiteration pattern. The author used only the first name to refer to the theme of clause 1. The logical relation is shown because the author did not use a preposition to refer to “Bettina Galang”. This can be attributed to the avoidance of committing missing antecedents among the pronouns or to avoid confusion among the readers.

The theme reiteration pattern is also observed in the theme “I” of clause 3 and the theme “I” of clause 5. The pattern promotes coherence among the themes as the story introduce other characters in the clause 4. The theme “I” is also observed in the theme reiteration pattern in clauses 5, 10, and 15. The use of pronouns in writing helps readers to understand the topic of the sentence.

The split theme pattern is also evident in the first paragraph of the short story. The rheme of the clause 9 is the “it” of the theme of clause 25, The rheme of clause 22 is the theme “The other half” of clause 26, and the rheme of clause 24 is the theme “the rest of the day” of clause 27. The split theme pattern is formed when the rheme of a clause relates to the theme of other clauses in the paragraph.

The first paragraphs utilized multiple thematic patterns. The complexity of the progressions helps the readers understand and appreciate the text better. Furthermore, it also adds aesthetic value to the story. This is supported by Pangetsu et al. (2019) who stated that the role of thematic progression is to establish the organization of the texts and its understanding. This clearly shows that the application of multiple thematic progression patterns is useful in building the overall connections of the ideas.

Conclusions

Based on the findings transcended from the data gathered, the following results are presented:

(1)The thematic selections used in the first paragraphs of the Don Carlos Palanca award-winning short stories analyzed utilized more on textual Themes specifically external conjunctions and continuatives. These themes were used as cohesive devices to establish connection between the clauses. There were interpersonal themes found in the text but it is outnumbered by textual themes. The textual themes and interpersonal themes are optional themes. Textual themes were utilized more because of its cohesive property that expresses continuity of ideas of the writers. The topical theme being the obligatory theme was categorized with its markedness. The data revealed that the marked themes were complexes and prepositional phrase was the most common type of complex marked theme. The unmarked themes mostly occurred in simple declarative clauses.

(2)The thematic progressions employed by the first paragraphs of Don Carlos Palanca award-winning short stories analyzed have combinations of different thematic progression patterns. The paragraphs used the constant theme pattern, linear theme pattern, and split-theme pattern. It was found out that in a complicated text where the context is established as the text develops, multiple thematic progression contributes in creating semantic relationship between the clauses. The relatedness of the clauses in the progression was attributed to the cohesive devices used by the authors. The textual themes utilized were the key factor in the development of meaning of the texts.

(3)Theme-Based Framework in Writing

Rationale

Writing is one of the language skills in English that should be mastered by students, especially high school students. They are demanded to be able to write a text because they have been taught how to write a text in school. They must consider many things such as grammar, vocabulary, mechanics and cohesion/coherence among sentences and paragraphs. Therefore, it is the responsibility of teachers to make their students master how to write a text properly as they have knowledge and capability of delivering theme-based writing in the process of teaching and learning.

The proposed theme-based framework in writing aims to provide teachers a guide to teach students coherence in writing. Through providing students theme-based writing activities, they will have more grammatical resources for them to construct coherent texts (Jing, 2015). The framework will equip the learner's opportunity to improve their writing styles through awareness of flow of ideas of the text guided by the concepts of theme selection and theme progression.

Theme-Based Framework in Teaching Writing

The study proposed this theme-based framework in writing based on the findings. The framework is composed of 4 sections that suggest a cycle in teaching writing to the students.

The circle is divided into four quadrants. Each quadrant has specific areas to develop to enhance the students' writing skills. The first quadrant refers to the teaching of thematic selection. The teaching of thematic selection prepares the students to identify proper cohesive devices in consideration to the logical relation they want to express. It will also help the students to establish the semantic relationship between the Rheme of the previous clause to the Theme of the succeeding clause. Based on the findings of the study, the authors of the award-winning pieces have well-structured Theme-Rheme connection. The students will be taught functional grammar as the basis of understanding the different functions of the words in the Theme section. As employed in the award-winning pieces, this portion will focus more on the role of cohesive devices in the Theme section to establish the connection among the different parts of the paragraph. This will also provide transition for the content for the second quadrant.

The second quadrant is the teaching of thematic progression. In this area, the students will be taught to track down the interplay of their clauses. The plotting of progression will enable them to trace the thought of their composition. Based on the findings of the study, the award-winning short stories employed different thematic progression pattern to express their ideas. In this portion, the students will receive inputs about the different thematic progression patterns and taught how to integrate different patterns together to create a multiple-theme pattern.

The third quadrant is the practice writing. The students will be asked to write a short composition consisting of few clauses. The students will identify the themes they used and its role in meaning development. They will also track the thematic progression they subscribed to and reflect on the interplay of their theme and rheme. In this portion, the teacher will aid the students in meaning development.

The fourth quadrant is the independent writing. This portion will require the students to write their compositions. The students will not be mentored in this area to enable them to practice their writing skills independently.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are given:

1. Teachers may include the concepts of thematic selection and thematic progression in writing classes.
2. Teachers may be trained how to utilize this theme-based framework to teach writing in their LAC (Learning Action Cell) session.
3. Future researchers may conduct the analysis of textual metafunction in students' writing composition to establish their gaps in writing.
4. Future researchers may conduct a different study about the analysis of textual metafunction of different academic papers to develop a framework in teaching academic writing.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study had obtained an exemption based on the nature of the study, for it purely utilized selected award-winning short stories of Filipino writers, and consent to use their masterpieces was asked before conducting this study.

Acknowledgments

The success of the study would not have been possible without the help of certain individuals who rendered aid beyond their line of duty for the fulfillment of this study. A heartfelt thanks and gratitude to the following people for assisting the researcher to finish his study through the proficiency they shared.

First of all, the Almighty God, for the guidance and enlightenment of mind and for giving his good health and strength in overcoming challenges in conducting this study; Dr. Ramon A. Boloron, the researcher's understanding adviser, for having selflessly shared some of his precious time in going through and giving feedback for this research output;

The panel of examiners headed by Dr. Roque A. Bongcac, Dean of the College of Education with members Fr. Dr. Ruel F. Lero, SVD, University President, and Dr. Socorro Anne R. Zaluaga, Program Head, BA Communication and General Education, for assisting the researcher to finish his study through the proficiency they shared; Dr. Mary Grace C. Ramada, the external member of the panel of examiners, for sharing her important time and information in improving the study; Mr. Rico C. Kionisala, very supportive friend whose guidance and expertise helped the researcher come up this output; Mrs. Maria Lourdes Culpa, for her encouragement that made the researcher continue doing his research;

His beloved family, for the everlasting provision, prayers and financial assistance made possible for the pursuit and completion of this study; Finally, everyone who extended their service and support to the researcher in any means possible, thank you so much. May God bless you!

REFERENCES

- Atlee, N. (2005). Writing Lab retrieved July 2, 2022, from <https://www.amazon.co.uk/Writing-Lab-Nancy-Atlee/dp/1593631499>
- Abola, A. Phallic Symbols. Don Carlos Palanca First Prize Award for Short Story 2015. Retrieved from https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bB_y9altsvZVnoMvWUG7L18pmy4CgCuN/view.
- Afrin, S. (2016). Writing problems of non-English major undergraduate students in Bangladesh: An observation. *Open journal of social sciences*, 4(03), 104.
- Bengan, J. Disguise. Don Carlos Palanca First Prize Award for Short Story 2017. Retrieved from <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1b4b49HV8lp2l-1VcwXDwtlZSE9URybkd/view>.
- Brown and Hood (1989). *Writing Matters - Writing Skills- and Strategies for Students of English*. Retrieved on July 2, 2022 from <https://www.scribd.com/document/407105128/Kristine-Brown-Susan-Hood-Writing-Matters-Writing-Skills-and-Strategies-for-Students-of-English-1989-pdf>
- Cornelio, R. Zoetrope. Don Carlos Palanca First Prize Award for Short Story 2016. Retrieved from <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BUfD2HXF8nRVcn9FSUuqWLL9hUILM3Yx/view>.
- Defazio, J., Jones, J., Tennant, F., & Hook, S.A. (2010). Academic literacy: The importance and impact of writing across the curriculum – a case study. *Journal of Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 10(2), pp. 34-47.
- Fang, D. & Li, S. (2015). Thematic Structure and Its Application to English Writing. 2nd International Conference on Education Reform and Modern Management. Retrieved from <https://www.atlantispress.com/article/20893.pdf>.
- Fang, F. G. (2018). Review of English as a medium of instruction in Chinese universities today: Current trends and future directions: New language policies to promote multilingualism and language support for EMI will be needed in Chinese tertiary contexts. *English Today*, 34(1), 32-37.

- Feng, Z. (2013). Functional Grammar and Its Implications for English Teaching and Learning. *English Language Teaching*, 6(10), 86-94.
- Graham, S. (2019). Changing How Writing is Taught. *Review of Research in Education*, 3(1). DOI <https://doi.org/10.3102/0091732X18821125>.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1985). *Introduction to Functional Grammar*. London: Edward Arnold.
- Halliday, M.A.K., Hasan, R. (1976). *Cohesion in English*. Longman Group Limited. Retrieved from https://kupdf.net/download/cohesion-in-english-halliday-amp-hasan-1976_58cb70e0dc0d60db13c34635_pdf.
- Halliday, M.A.K. & Matthiessen, C. (2004). *An Introduction to Functional Grammar Third Edition*. Oxford University Press, NY10016.
- Jing, W. (2015). Theme and Thematic Progression in English Writing Teaching. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(21). Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1079122.pdf>.
- Lahuerta, A. (2015). Use of Conjunctions in the Compositions of Secondary Education Students. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 212:42-46. DOI: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.11.296.
- Li, Y. (2021). Appraisal Meanings of English Comment Adjuncts and their Motivations Vol. 9 No. 11 November 2021 <https://www.ijern.com/journal/2021/November-2021/04.pdf>
- Mardani, T. (2016). Marked and Unmarked Thematization Patterns: A Contrastive Study of Persuasive Texts Written by Native and Non-Native English Columnists. *Review of Applied Linguistics Research*, 2(2), 14-43.
- Mulcahy, M. & Gouldthorp, B. (2015). Positioning the reader: the effect of narrative point-of-view and familiarity of experience on situation model construction. *Cambridge University Press, Language and Cognition Journal*, 8(1). 96-123. doi:10.1017/langcog.2014.45.
- Pablo, J.C. & Lasaten, R.C. (2018). Writing Difficulties and Quality of Academic Essays of Senior High School Students. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(4), pp. 46-57. Retrieved from <http://www.apjmr.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/APJMR-2018-6.4.06.pdf>.
- Paltridge, B. (2000). *Making Sense of Discourse analysis*. Gold Coast, Queensland: Antipodean Educational Enterprises.
- Paltridge, B. (2006). *Discourse Analysis*. London: Continuum Books. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2902453>
- Pangetsu, G., Harvian, E.D., & Suprijadi, D. (2019). Thematic Progression in Students' Descriptive Text. DOI 10.22460/project.v2i4.p575-580.
- Saavedra, A. (2020). Factors that Contribute to the Poor Writing Skills in Filipino and English of Elementary Pupils. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity, and Change*. Retrieved from [https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3697915#:~:text=Based%20on%20their%20experiences%20and,in%20writing%3B%20and%205\)%20the.](https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3697915#:~:text=Based%20on%20their%20experiences%20and,in%20writing%3B%20and%205)%20the.)
- Ulit, J. L. (2018). Writing Errors of Grade Nine Students: Basis for Sentence Writing Module. <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-5860-3010> jhonathan.ulit15@gmail.com <https://aseanresearch.org/downloads/astr/publication/2/ARTICLE%202.%20ULIT.pdf>

Vethamani, M. E., Manaf, U. K. A., & Akbari, O. (2008). Students' Use of Modals in Narrative Compositions: Forms and Functions. *English Language Teaching*, 1(1), 61-74.